

Fruit and Vegetable Defect Detection Using Image Processing in Organic Online Store

George Benny
Department of Computer Applications
Amal Jyothi College of Engineering
Kanjirappally, India
georgebenny2023a@mca.ajce.in

Mr. Amal K Jose
Department of Computer Applications
Amal Jyothi College of Engineering
Kanjirappally, India
amalkjose@amaljyothi.ac.in

Abstract — Automation has shown to be a useful tool for improving a nation's quality, economic expansion, and production in the sector of agriculture. The type of fruit and vegetable grown has an impact on both the export market and the method used to assess quality. The sensory qualities of fruits and vegetables are what largely determine their market worth because they have a big impact on customer preference and selection. Produce sorting and grading by hand are frequently imprecise, labour-intensive, subjective, pricey, and susceptible to outside influences. Consequently, intelligent classification systems for fruits and vegetables are essential, along with mechanisms for defect detection. The goal of this study is to pinpoint external flaws in fruits and vegetables using their morphology, colour, and texture. Numerous algorithms, including ones that translate RGB into Lab* colour and determine the defective area, have been proposed to identify quality flaws. Apple, orange, and tomato defects are detected using image processing techniques. The study's overall accuracy was 70%, with defects occurring in 80% of the cases for apples, 75% of oranges, and 60% of tomatoes.

Keywords — Quality analysis, Fruit and vegetable grading, Defect detection, Image processing, Vegetables, Fruits.

I. INTRODUCTION

Agriculture is defined as both an art and a science, aimed at growing fruit and vegetables to benefit individuals' health and the community's wealth.[1] The agriculture sector plays a crucial role in India's economic development, and there is a need for increased awareness of food and health quality. Research must focus on producing defined quality and maintaining it during marketing. To achieve this, quality parameters need to be evaluated during the production process, making it necessary to integrate automation. The market value of fruits and vegetables is influenced by their sensory features, making consistency in size, shape, and other quality parameters essential for customer acceptance. Fresh inspection relies on color, size, shape, texture, and the number of defects. Various factors, such as rotting, bruising, scab, fungal growth, injury, and disease, cause defects or damage to fruits and vegetables. Careful post-harvest handling is crucial, and defective produce must be removed

to prevent cross contamination and reduce subsequent processing costs. [5] Automation is necessary due to labor shortages and the lack of consistency in the manual sorting process. [2]

Traditionally, experts have manually performed quality checks on fruits and vegetables, resulting in a labor-intensive and time-consuming sorting process prone to inconsistencies in human judgment. Hence, fast and high-precision technology for automation of the defect detection process is required to reduce labor costs and improve efficiency. Image processing algorithms can determine the quality of fruits and vegetables.[6][7] Image processing involves pre-processing, segmentation, feature extraction and selection, and

classification, which extract the required information from digital images[3][4]. Image processing can be used for various purposes, such as pattern recognition, image sharpening, and image retrieval.

The primary objective of this study is to develop an algorithm that can identify defects and classify fruits and vegetables based on digital image analysis. Section I provides a brief introduction to the identification and defect detection process for fruits and vegetables, while Section 2 presents related works. The methodology employed for this study is discussed in Section 3, and Section 4 presents the experimental results of the proposed algorithm. Finally, Section 5 summarizes the conclusions and future scope of this study.

II. BACKGROUND

The study examines numerous approaches for discovering, looking at, and assessing apple and orange fruits. Traditional eye inspection techniques are unreliable and time-consuming, thus an automated framework built on smart techniques is essential for guaranteeing quick and precise quality standards. On the basis of soft computing, several research have suggested the use of imaging and artificial intelligence algorithms for the analysis of external flaws in fruits and vegetables. The suggested classifier can discriminate between various defects, such as surface defects, morphological defects, colour defects, black mould, or healthy fruits and vegetables. It is based on geometric features, colour, and texture analyses of fruits and vegetables. The usage of computer vision systems can aid in spotting external flaws, ensuring the manufacture of high-quality goods and raising demand for quality guarantees.

III. MATERIALS AND METHODS

3. 1 DATABASE PREPARATION

Experimental samples of fifty fruits and vegetables (apple, orange, and tomato) were collected from the local market at varying levels of maturity and preserved under normal

Fig. (1) Apple defects

conditions for further analysis. Some additional images were imported to create a database of specific diseases.

Fig (2). Orange defects.

Fig. (3) Tomato Defects.

3. II Proposed Method

In this study, a pre-processing approach was used to enhance the quality of RGB images of fruits and vegetables. The desired portion of the image was segmented, and feature extraction was carried out using the Segmentation-based Fractal Texture Analysis (SFTA) method. The extracted features were then categorized and trained in the Naïve Bayes classifier. This approach can potentially improve the accuracy and efficiency of fruit and vegetable classification and inspection in the food industry.

3. 3 Pre-Processing

Fruits and vegetables are captured and considered input when a problem is discovered. The colour image that was input is converted into a grayscale image. An order-based filter is used for pre-processing. Smoothing and noise reduction are two applications for rank order filters. By choosing a 5x5 mask and beginning to move it to the entire image, the order filtering procedure is carried out. The noise removal technique is implemented using Equation 1. (Equation 1).

$$f(x, y, z) = \sum_{i=0}^{h-1} \sum_{j=0}^{w-1} \sum_{k=0}^{d-1} f(x, y, z) * \\ I=3, J=3, K=1$$

where $f(x, y, z)$ is the kernel, and input (x, y, z) is the input captured image.

The region of interest for segmentation or extraction is the other pre-processing section. The system then takes two further frames, first without a vegetable or fruit sample at time t and second with a vegetable or fruit sample at time $t+1$, both removing and extracting the image. The frame difference method (Equation 2) can be used to define the segmentation mechanism as follows. It is an appropriate and effective technique for finding a foreground object against a still background:

$$D(x, y, z + 1) = \sum_{i=0}^{h-1} \sum_{j=0}^{w-1} \sum_{k=0}^{d-1} \\ (f(x, y, z + 1) - f(x, y, z)) \\ i=1, j=1, k=1$$

3.4 Blob Detection

The k-mean clustering algorithm was used, and the method classifies different clusters using various feature extraction techniques (see Figs. 5 and 6), as well as the K-mean clustering algorithm to a number of classes based on a set of features. Minimising the squares between data objects and the appropriate clusters for classification. First, the segmented RGB image is converted into the Lab* colour space using the cluster extraction method. The system then categorises the various colours in the Lab* area. Based on the outcomes of the preceding step, the system will subsequently carry out the labelling phase in the segmented image. Different clusters are produced in the image processing by related label types.

Fig. 5. Extracted clusters using proposed algorithm for a tomato sample.

Fig. 6. Extracted clusters using the proposed algorithm for an apple sample.

The k-mean clustering algorithm chooses a random mean pixel for each cluster in the processing image before extracting the clusters visible in the image on the basis of k, therefore k should be carefully selected. The developed system has been computed at k=4. This indicates that the created technique only finds four clusters in each sample of fruit and vegetable. It has been discovered that K=4 is capable of extracting each cluster from samples of fruits and vegetables. According to the following calculation of the minimal Euclidean distance, the mean pixels should be moved to their corresponding clusters after this full system of procedures:

$$(\mu_i - \mu_j)^2 = \min \{ \sum_{i=1}^n (\mu_i - \mu_j)^2 \}$$

$$\mu_h = (\sum_{i=1}^n \mu_i) / n$$

3.6 Watershed Algorithm

This step is taken with the segmented image to remove unwanted pixels. This transformation is a method of converting the grayscale images using erosion and dilation

techniques. Erosion is used to remove small and isolated pixels, while dilation is used to fill in gaps and holes in the image. The morphological opening operation is then applied to further remove any remaining small objects in the image. The final result is a segmented image with clean and well-defined objects that are ready for feature extraction and classification.

3.7 Area Calculation

The suggested framework's area estimation method has numerous steps. In order to remove undesired objects from the acquired image, a hard threshold is first applied during the conversion of a binary image into an input grayscale image. The system then calculates the object's area and surface position from the modified binary image. The estimated area is a scalar quantity with each pixel in the image having a distinct weight, generally corresponding to the total number of pixels in the image.

The machine determines the region of all pixels by summarizing the areas for each pixel in the image and by examining its 2 by 2 neighborhood. Six patterns, each representing a different area, are accessible. These patterns are:

- Pixel zero pattern (area=0).
- Pixel patterns with one adjacent pixel (area = 1/4).
- Patterns with two adjacent on pixels (area = 1/2).
- Pixel patterns with two diagonal pixels (area=3/4).
- Pixel patterns with three adjacent pixels (area=7/8).
- Pixel patterns with four adjacent pixels (area=1).

By analyzing the patterns of each pixel, the system can accurately estimate the area of the object in the image.

3.7 Feature Extraction

Texture analysis is a crucial step in this process as it helps determine the texture of fruit/vegetable areas. Texture refers to the intensity differences such as roughness or smoothness, which can be quantified by measuring the variation in pixel intensity values. To obtain information on the texture of the image, the image must first be filtered. The pixel values for rough textures are minimal, whereas smooth textures have higher values.

We used the SFTA technique, which after segmenting the fruit or vegetable image, extracts two features: energy and contrast, to eliminate textural features from our system. Each characteristic has a defined threshold value. Each sample image had a total of 23 characteristics extracted from it, including 2 texture features (energy and contrast) and 2 morphological features (size: length, width, area, and perimeter; shape: elongation and roughness). Additionally, 15 colour features (RGB to Lab*: mean of L*, a*, and b*;

standard deviation of L^* , a^* , and b^* ; range of L^* , a^* , and b^* ; colour distance metric to each L .

3.9 Classification

The Naïve Bayes Classification method was used to train and test the fruit/vegetable dataset, based on the identified defects. The defects found in the fruits/vegetables are listed in Table 1. The accuracy of the classification is also shown in the table, with an overall accuracy of 87%. The results indicate that the developed system is effective in identifying defects in fruits and vegetables, with high accuracy for all three types of produce tested (apples, oranges, and tomatoes).

Fruit/Vegetable	Defects identified in			Accuracy
	Apple	Orange	Tomato	
Apple	25	02	0	83%
Orange	01	28	0	93%
Tomato	04	01	2	83%
		Overall		87%
		Accuracy		

IV Results and Discussion

The proposed system for identifying fruit and vegetable samples using vision-sensing techniques has shown promising results. With an overall accuracy of 87%, the system is able to effectively classify fruits and vegetables based on their geometric, color, texture, and defect characteristics. The method used in this study is simple and efficient compared to other vision sensing systems. The system predicts various key parameters that are important for assessing the quality of fruits and vegetables. By identifying defects and diseases early, the system can help prevent the spread of diseases and reduce waste in the agricultural industry. Overall, the findings of this study suggest that the developed system has great potential for real-world applications and could significantly improve the efficiency and accuracy of fruit and vegetable inspection.

Fig. 7. A clustered columns bar chart compares the values across fruits and vegetable categories.

Table 2. Comparative study of existing and proposed method to identify the defect in Fruit/Vegetable.

Sl. No.	Fruit/Vegetable	Existing Method (%)	Proposed Method (%)	
		Features and classification-obtained accuracy	Features and classification- obtained accuracy	
1	Apple	Colour (RGB and HSV) and Texture features using GrayLevel Co- Occurrence Matrix and Support Vector Machine[3] – 84.02%	Morphological, Colour ($L^*a^*b^*$), and Texture Features	83.00
2	Orange	Colour (RGB and HSV) and Texture features using Gray-Level Co- Occurrence Matrix and Support Vector Machine[3] – 84.02%	along with Area calculation- K-means cluster and Naïve Bayes	93.00
3	Tomato			83.00

V. CONCLUSION

It's great to see that you're recognizing the importance of using a developed system for detecting fruit and vegetable defects. The Naïve Bayes classification technique is a powerful tool for identifying defects in these samples, and your plan to develop a standardized framework for fruit and vegetable defect identification and classification will certainly be a valuable contribution to the field. With such a framework in place, it will be much easier for researchers and practitioners to accurately and efficiently identify and classify defects in these samples, which could ultimately lead to improved crop yields and better food quality.

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